

PMP Pilot Survey Palestine

Methodological Report

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Sample and Methodology

The survey included a two-stage stratified sample:

The first stage: The territory of the West bank is divided in three regions: South governorates (including Hebron and Bethlehem), Central governorates (including Ramallah, Jerusalem and Jericho), and Northern governorates (including Nablus, Jenin, Tulkarm, Tubas, Salfit and Qalqilia). Within each region, 5 localities were selected (in total, 15 localities) in a way to reflect the country's socio-demographic diversity with regard to factors such as religiosity, urbanism, economic conditions, past conflict exposure and the type of residential community. Specifically, in each region, 2 urban, 2 rural localities and one camp were selected.

The second stage: After visiting the localities selected in the first stage; the interviewers looked for one person (seed) from each locality. Seed respondents complied with the following criteria:

- They have 18 years or more at the time of the survey.
- They have been living in the local area for the last 5 years.
- They do not have a formal leader role in the local area (e.g., as a religious leader or political representative).

The remaining respondents were selected by using controlled network sampling method, starting with contact networks of seed respondents. This was accomplished by asking each respondent during face-to-face interview to name all adults with whom he or she had talked about the past in the last three months and to indicate where each of these people currently live. Subsequent respondents were randomly selected by interviewers from among network members who live in the same area as the respondent using random numbers table. More specifically, network members who were aged 18 or more at the time of the survey, live in the same local area, but not in the same household as the referring respondent, were presumed to be eligible for participation. An approximate of 22 respondents (including seed respondent) were interviewed in each locality.

Questionnaire preparation

Two questionnaires (versions 1 and 2) in were provided by the investigators. The two questionnaire versions were administered simultaneously, and they were randomly assigned to the respondents. The original questionnaires were revised to better conform to the format to which local interviewers are used to. The questionnaires were originally developed in English

and translated to Arabic by a translator. The Arabic version was then checked and corrected by the local PMP team.

The research team

The research team consisted of the PMP researchers - Randa Nasser, the local project coordinator, and Mai Albzour, the PMP doctoral student; and Walid Iadadwa's survey team. The survey team consisted of 15 interviewers, who had an experience of fieldwork and have worked previously in similar studies. For every five interviewers a field supervisor was appointed (the total number of supervisors was 3). On a daily basis, they ensured that the interviewers arrived to the selected interview locations, followed correct procedures to reach respondents and had questionnaires and other materials and used correct formats; they further reviewed the collected data and give feedback to interviewers; finally, they collected the completed forms and delivered them to the coordinator. Walid Iadadwa oversees the work of the whole team as a general coordinator.

Interviewer training

The training workshop was held on 16/7/2016 in the presence of the PMP and the whole survey team. During the workshop interviewers were trained in administering the questionnaire, respondents' selection and interview conduct. All interviewers were instructed to conduct a practice interview with an acquaintance.

Fieldwork

Before starting the fieldwork, envelopes have been prepared including all survey material: questionnaires, life calendar for the version 1, contact sheets, response cards and appendices with illustrations. The fieldwork started on 17/7/2016 and finished on 31/7/2016. The interviewers were followed daily by the supervisor and coordinator to assure that the procedures have been followed. All completed questionnaires were checked by the supervisors to assure that they were completed correctly. About 20 % of questionnaires were backchecked by the supervisors and coordinator who contacted and visited the respondents. Interviewers and Supervisors were instructed to write fieldnotes and note all encountered problems. At the end of the fieldwork, a debriefing session was organized with all interviewers.

Data entry

The PMP team provided a SPSS template file. Data entry personnel has been trained and then entered the data.